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Ifqar: Signs of Involvement in Economic Warfare from Individual Perspective

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Abstract

Economic warfare is traditionally associated with poverty, but a more nuanced understanding reveals it as a deliberate effort to impoverish individuals or groups, a process termed *Ifqar* (to make poor). Unlike general poverty, economic warfare involves coercion or force, where individuals are systematically deprived of economic opportunities and resources. This article explores the nature and mechanisms of economic warfare, including forced unemployment, denial of capital, and artificially enhancing competitors through fraud or nepotism. External actors such as employers, competitors, and institutions play key roles in sabotaging individuals' economic stability. These tactics not only lead to financial hardship but also exert severe psychological pressure on victims, who struggle to maintain ethical values in hostile environments. The broader societal impact includes diminished economic power and reduced access to resources, which further weakens communities. Economic warfare, characterized by deliberate coercion, poses significant challenges to individuals and society, requiring a deep understanding to foster fairer economic policies.

Keywords: Ifqar, Economic warfare

Introduction

Economic warfare is often associated with poverty from a general perspective, but from a more nuanced viewpoint, it can be described as a deliberate effort to impoverish individuals or groups, a process known as *Ifqar* (from the Arabic term meaning "to make poor"). The term *Ifqar* is the antithesis of *afkhar* (to enrich or exalt), and it occurs when a person is forcibly dragged down from their position of stability or prosperity. In this context, the presence of coercion or force is essential to define the situation as economic warfare. Mere poverty, absent of forceful actions, cannot be perceived as a battleground in this context.

This article aims to explore the nature of economic warfare, the mechanisms through which it unfolds, and the impact it has on individuals and society at large. By analyzing the signs and tactics used in such conflicts, we can better understand how economic warfare operates both on an individual and systemic level.

Defining Economic Warfare

Forced Impoverishment (*Ifqar*)

The essence of economic warfare lies in the forced impoverishment of individuals, often carried out through mechanisms designed to prevent access to economic opportunities or resources. Examples include:

1. **Unemployment despite capability:** One hallmark of economic warfare is deliberately keeping competent individuals out of employment, even when they possess the necessary skills and qualifications. This tactic strips them of their means of livelihood and can force them into a state of financial insecurity.
2. **Lack of investment for capable individuals:** Another sign of economic warfare is the inability to secure capital to start or continue a business despite having the requisite experience and expertise. This is not due to a lack of potential but rather an intentional blockade to prevent economic progression.

3. **Artificially enhanced competitors:** The creation of false or inflated capabilities among competitors through fraud, favoritism, or manipulation of systems is another weapon in economic warfare. By creating fake merit or manipulating processes, undeserving individuals or entities are placed in favorable positions, sidelining those who truly adhere to standards and ethics.

These strategies represent a systematic effort to undermine individuals and groups, pulling them into economic battlegrounds where the odds are stacked against them.

Mechanisms of Economic Warfare

The Role of Employers, Rivals, and Institutions

Economic warfare does not necessarily begin with the affected individual. Instead, it is often initiated by external actors such as employers, rivals, banks, governments, or even hostile foreign states. These actors can engage in tactics that sabotage the economic well-being of individuals or groups, intentionally creating hardships. For example, employers may deliberately dismiss highly qualified employees (PhDs, postdoctoral researchers, etc.) to prevent them from completing specialized projects due to a lack of funding or resources. This not only hinders their professional growth but also pushes them into economic instability.

Rivals also play a significant role in economic warfare. By falsifying qualifications and inflating their résumés with worthless achievements, they can secure positions that rightfully belong to those who adhere to ethical standards. This undermines the integrity of merit-based employment and research, pushing capable individuals into a battle for survival in an unfair competitive environment.

Nepotism and Favoritism

Another aspect of economic warfare is nepotism or favoritism in hiring practices, which further exacerbates economic inequality. In many cases, competent individuals are excluded from opportunities due to preferential treatment given to less qualified individuals with personal or political connections. This, in turn, forces those with genuine talent and expertise into a disadvantaged economic position, further fueling their struggles.

Nepotism can distort labor markets and perpetuate cycles of poverty and inequality, making it one of the more insidious tools of economic warfare. Those who rely on honesty, integrity, and hard work may find themselves systematically excluded from opportunities, thereby pushing them further into economic marginalization.

The Psychological Toll of Economic Warfare

Economic warfare does not only manifest in material deprivation. It also imposes severe psychological pressure on its victims, who may find themselves constantly at odds with a system that seems designed to work against them. The constant effort to maintain ethical standards, such as absolute honesty, diligence, and morality, often proves detrimental in an environment where these traits are not rewarded. This "war on values" can be just as damaging as the financial hardships imposed by economic warfare, leading individuals to question the fairness of the system and their place within it.

Systemic Impacts on Society

Economic warfare also has broader societal implications. It can lead to the overall degradation of a community's economic power, particularly when large segments of the population are unable to access employment, capital, or other resources necessary for financial stability. This reduces the overall purchasing power of society and negatively impacts the quality of life for all. The decline in income, reduced access to housing, and limited opportunities for recreation and food security are symptoms of an economically weakened society.

However, for individuals caught in the direct line of economic warfare, the burden is even heavier. In these cases, the element of "coercion" is even more pronounced, as they are often systematically targeted through overt or covert means to ensure their economic disenfranchisement.

Conclusion

Economic warfare is a multifaceted and complex phenomenon, with far-reaching consequences for individuals and society at large. The strategies used in such warfare, from deliberate unemployment to artificial enhancement of competitors, aim to impoverish individuals and exclude them from economic participation. By examining the

mechanisms behind these actions, it becomes evident that economic warfare is not simply a byproduct of natural market forces but rather a targeted and deliberate strategy designed to maintain control and dominance over resources and opportunities.

To address the challenges posed by economic warfare, it is essential to recognize its signs and understand the systemic and individual impacts. Only then can society begin to implement policies and practices that foster economic fairness and prevent the continued marginalization of capable individuals.

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Terrorism or Anti-Apartheid: A Multi-National Overview

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Abstract

International terrorism is a complex phenomenon that involves not just individuals, but multiple states and governments, such as Germany, Israel, and the United States. This article explores the role of international terrorism in perpetuating systemic inequalities, or "apartheid," through military, economic, informational, and even scientific means. It highlights the impact on victims of this international terrorism and advocates for resistance against all forms of apartheid—whether economic, scientific, artistic, political, or legal—as a necessary step towards achieving freedom and justice. The article emphasizes the importance of confronting these multifaceted forms of oppression, particularly when they manifest in extreme economic disparities, such as the exorbitant costs of military actions that disproportionately affect vulnerable populations like Palestinian children.

Keywords: Terrorism, Apartheid

Introduction

The concept of international terrorism extends beyond individual actors to encompass the actions of multiple states and governments that leverage various tools to advance their interests at the expense of others. Countries such as Germany, Israel, and the United States are often cited as examples of state actors involved in what can be termed "international terrorism." This form of terrorism is not limited to violent acts but also includes economic, informational, and even scientific strategies, which foster systemic inequality or apartheid that disproportionately benefits a powerful minority. The misuse of globally accepted "good terms" to justify acts of violence and terrorism, particularly in relation to major constitutional crimes such as those seen in Gaza, has been thoroughly examined (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024a). Notably, these misused terms extend beyond rhetorical manipulation, influencing diplomatic practices and becoming complicit in criminal misconduct by the states involved (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024b).

The Nature of International Terrorism

International terrorism can be understood as a form of violence that is perpetrated not only through physical means but also through economic, informational, and scientific channels. States accused of engaging in international terrorism employ a variety of tools, such as military interventions, economic sanctions, and propaganda campaigns, to further their political agendas. For instance, military interventions in conflict zones, such as Palestine, can be seen as acts of state terrorism that aim to suppress resistance and control resources. The use of such tools often results in a form of international apartheid that segregates and oppresses the weaker sections of society, creating an imbalance that favors the powerful elite.

Struggles Against Apartheid

The struggle for international rights is inherently tied to the battle against apartheid, and vice versa. Those who understand this connection will have a clearer view of the fronts where these battles must be fought. Apartheid, as a system, is not just a structure built upon the earth; it is a concept rooted in a higher, more pervasive

form of injustice. As mentioned in the Quran: "I am better than him; You created me from fire and created him from clay" (Al-A'raf 7:12). This verse highlights the arrogance that often underpins discrimination, a mindset at the core of apartheid. Believing that apartheid is created from "clay" means acknowledging its earthly origins and recognizing that one must rise with the fervor of "fire" to dismantle it.

The comparison between apartheid and fire emphasizes the intensity and commitment required to challenge systems of oppression. Just as fire has the ability to consume and transform, so must the struggle against apartheid aim to eradicate its foundations. Only by adopting such a resolute approach can true justice be achieved on both local and international levels (Mandela, 1994; Said, 1979).

Economic Apartheid as a Tool of Oppression

Economic apartheid refers to the systemic exclusion of certain groups from economic opportunities and resources. This is evident in situations where the cost of a single bomb dropped on Palestinian children exceeds the annual wages of hundreds of people. This stark economic disparity reflects the existence of an economic system that prioritizes military expenditure over the basic needs of people. The international community's failure to address these economic inequalities perpetuates a system of economic apartheid that disproportionately affects vulnerable populations (Chomsky, 2020).

Informational and Scientific Apartheid

Apart from economic apartheid, informational and scientific apartheid are also prevalent in international terrorism. Informational apartheid involves the manipulation and control of media narratives to shape public opinion in favor of the powerful elite. This can be seen in the biased coverage of conflicts where the aggressor is portrayed as the victim and the victim as the aggressor. Similarly, scientific apartheid refers to the use of scientific knowledge and resources to develop advanced weaponry and surveillance technologies that are used to oppress and control populations (Finkelstein, 2018).

Resistance Against All Forms of Apartheid

Resistance against all forms of apartheid—economic, informational, scientific, artistic, political, and legal—is essential to achieving freedom and justice. Those who act against these forms of oppression are often considered freedom fighters. For instance, activists who challenge economic apartheid by advocating for equitable distribution of resources, or who resist informational apartheid by exposing media biases, play a crucial role in the fight for justice. The need for pragmatic action against all forms of apartheid is essential for achieving a just society (Said, 1992).

The Cost of Inaction

The cost of inaction in the face of international terrorism and apartheid is immense. When people fail to act against systemic injustices, they inadvertently contribute to the perpetuation of these systems. The economic cost of military actions, such as the high price of bombs dropped on civilian populations, highlights the urgent need for collective action against these oppressive systems. The struggle for lawful and equitable livelihoods is often met with barriers imposed by economic, military, and legal apartheid, necessitating a collective effort to dismantle these systems (Roy, 2009).

State Terrorism

State terrorism, particularly in the form of economic, psychological, and state-sponsored violence, is often justified under the guise of legality or international resolutions (Chomsky, 2001). In recent days, protests have taken place in Berlin, Hamburg, and other German cities against the government's arms shipments to the volatile Middle East. These protests were met with violent suppression by German military and paramilitary forces, resulting in the deaths of several protestors and the injury or deportation of others. The German government, however, has consistently placed the blame on Islamist groups, deflecting responsibility for the unrest (Klein, 2023).

Germany, with its historical record of state violence and radicalism, has again shifted towards ideological racism, this time under the guise of anti-Semitic-Arab policies. This new wave of racism, while echoing historical prejudices, now operates through a Zionist lens, as modern racism is shaped by ideologies that trace back to Herzl and the roots of Zionism (Pappe, 2017). The psychological, economic, and security well-being of populations in distant regions is once again under attack, driven by ideological forces emanating from Germany's foreign policies.

Further complicating the issue, some German military and paramilitary personnel have reportedly been involved with the Israeli Defense Forces (IDF) or have contributed in advisory roles, offering training to individuals linked to Zionist international crimes (Finkelstein, 2003). This reflects the growing role of Germany in supporting state-sponsored terrorism, often justified by legal frameworks but resulting in widespread violence and oppression, especially in the context of the Middle East.

Conclusion

International terrorism is not limited to the actions of rogue individuals or groups; it is a systemic issue involving multiple states and governments. The use of military, economic, informational, and scientific tools to create a favorable environment for a powerful minority is a form of international terrorism that perpetuates various forms of apartheid. To combat these forms of oppression, it is crucial to recognize and resist them in all their manifestations. Only through concerted efforts against economic, informational, scientific, and other forms of apartheid can a more just and equitable world be achieved.

Acknowledgement: Dr. Amirali R. Davoudpour is an associate professor at the Iranian Canon of Medicine and Law, a non-governmental organization dedicated to protecting the civil rights of Iranian and Afghan migrants. Nasim Amiri Ghadi is an M.A. student in the Faculty of Anthropology and Cultural Studies at Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan-Poland.

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Electoral Engineering and Non-Democratic Voting Practices: A Theoretical Review

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Abstract

Electoral engineering refers to a range of tactics employed by political actors to manipulate election outcomes, undermining the principles of democratic governance. By distorting voter behavior through various means, such as ethnic voting, vote buying, religious influences, and partisan loyalty, electoral engineering poses significant challenges to the legitimacy of elections. This paper offers a comprehensive theoretical review of electoral engineering and its impact on democratic processes. The study identifies and analyzes four main types of non-democratic voting practices and provides a framework for understanding their effects on democracy.

Keywords: Electoral engineering, Politics

Introduction

Democratic elections are designed to reflect the collective will of the people. However, the manipulation of electoral processes, often referred to as electoral engineering, distorts this principle. By manipulating the electoral environment, political elites can consolidate power, undermine public trust, and weaken democratic institutions. Electoral engineering includes a wide array of tactics aimed at skewing the results of elections, from controlling voter behavior to influencing the electoral landscape through districting or disenfranchisement (Birch, 2011). This article focuses on four forms of non-democratic voting practices often employed in electoral engineering: ethnic voting, vote buying, religious voting, and political voting.

The manipulation of electoral outcomes is not a new phenomenon. Scholars have long examined how political actors utilize various tools to secure electoral victories through means that undermine the integrity of the democratic process. Birch (2011) defines electoral engineering as any action taken to manipulate the conditions or the results of an election, often violating the fairness of the electoral process. This manipulation may take place at various stages, from redrawing district boundaries to controlling media narratives. Election manipulation is particularly effective in hybrid regimes, where elections are held but not free from manipulation (Levitsky & Way, 2010).

One of the key ways in which electoral engineering manifests is through non-democratic voting practices. These practices, such as vote buying, ethnic voting, and religious influence, divert elections away from a focus on policy and merit. According to Schedler (2002), electoral authoritarian regimes often rely on a façade of democratic elections to maintain legitimacy while simultaneously manipulating the process to ensure the ruling party's victory. Manipulating voter preferences and behaviors, electoral engineering undermines the very foundation of democracy by negating the idea of free and fair elections (Collier & Vicente, 2012). To understand the non-democratic practices in the electoral engineering an in-depth analysis of the concept of authenticity is evident (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024). Inauthentic votes are not considered a democratic elections by virtue and the countries which practice elections under an influence of inauthentic means are not considered democratic despite their vow for democracy and justice.

Types of Non-Democratic Voting Practices

1. Ethnic Voting

Ethnic voting occurs when voters align themselves with candidates from their own ethnic group, regardless of policy or competence. This form of voting is particularly prevalent in societies with deep ethnic divisions. Scholars such as Horowitz (1985) have demonstrated how ethnic affiliations can become the primary determinant of electoral outcomes in multi-ethnic societies. Ethnic voting contributes to the "ethnicization" of politics, where elections become contests of identity rather than platforms for policy debates (Posner, 2005).

Impact of Ethnic Votes on Democracy:

Ethnic voting promotes division within society and undermines democratic institutions by limiting the competition between candidates based on policy proposals. It also perpetuates political instability, as political parties increasingly cater to ethnic constituencies rather than broader national interests (Chandra, 2004). This fragmentation often results in political gridlock, as coalitions are formed not based on ideological alignment, but on ethnic compromise (Lijphart, 1999).

2. Vote Buying (Bus Votes)

Vote buying is the act of offering money or material incentives in exchange for votes. It is one of the most direct forms of electoral manipulation and is particularly effective in societies with high levels of poverty and inequality (Schaffer & Schedler, 2007). Studies show that vote buying not only distorts the electoral process but also diminishes voter engagement in post-election accountability. Instead of evaluating candidates based on their performance or policy agendas, voters are incentivized by short-term financial gains (Vicente, 2014).

Impact of Bus Votes on Democracy:

Vote buying reduces elections to mere economic transactions, weakening the representativeness of elected officials. It also undermines political accountability, as elected officials may feel less obligated to fulfill campaign promises or respond to the needs of their constituents if their electoral success is tied to financial power rather than voter support (Hicken, 2011). Furthermore, vote buying contributes to entrenched political corruption and perpetuates economic inequality (Stokes, 2005).

3. Religious Voting

Religious voting occurs when voters make decisions based on shared religious affiliations with candidates or religious endorsements. In many countries, religious identity plays a central role in shaping political behavior. Norris and Inglehart (2004) argue that in societies where religion is intertwined with national identity, religious leaders and institutions hold significant sway over voters. This phenomenon is particularly evident in countries with dominant state religions or where religious groups have deep social and political influence.

Impact of Religious Votes on Democracy:

While religious voting can reflect deeply held values, it also risks undermining the secular nature of democratic governance. It may marginalize minority religious groups and promote theocratic policies that conflict with pluralistic democratic principles (Philpott, 2007). Religious voting can also lead to the politicization of religious institutions, where religious figures gain undue influence over political outcomes, blurring the line between church and state (Haynes, 2009).

4. Political Voting

Political voting refers to casting votes based solely on party loyalty or ideological alignment, without consideration of the individual candidate's qualifications or local concerns. This form of voting can be particularly problematic in local elections, where voters may be swayed by national political debates rather than the merits of local candidates. Political voting often reinforces partisan divisions, making it difficult to achieve governance consensus, especially at the local level (Cox & McCubbins, 2005).

Impact of Political Votes on Democracy:

Excessive political voting at the local level can undermine the democratic principle of electing competent leaders based on their ability to address local issues. When voters prioritize party affiliation over competence, the quality of governance at the municipal level suffers (Dalton & Wattenberg, 2000). Political voting may also lead to polarization, with elected officials more focused on partisan battles than on solving problems affecting their constituencies (Fiorina & Abrams, 2008).

Conclusion

This review has outlined key forms of non-democratic voting practices used in electoral engineering, including ethnic voting, vote buying, religious voting, and political voting. These practices threaten the foundations of democracy by distorting voter behavior and undermining the integrity of the electoral process. Each of these voting practices reveals different ways in which electoral engineering can manipulate elections to favor specific groups or interests, often at the expense of broader national welfare.

Addressing the challenges posed by electoral engineering requires comprehensive reforms. Legal frameworks must be strengthened to enforce accountability and prevent practices such as vote buying. Civil society must play an active role in educating voters about the importance of informed, independent voting. Ultimately, the success of democracy depends on maintaining free, fair, and transparent electoral processes.

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